

GEOGRAPHICAL ASPECTS OF RECREATION-TOURIST ACTIVITY IN UZBEKISTAN

Bakhrieva Zarina Nasimovna

1st year doctoral student of "Silk Road" International University of Tourism and Cultural
Heritage

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Abstract. *Scientists from various fields of knowledge are engaged in recreation and tourism. They define their object and subject within the framework of their goals and tasks, as a result, they gave different interpretations to these concepts. Therefore, within the framework of these concepts, several controversial situations arise in the research conducted by geographers. This article aims to reveal the main meaning of the concepts of "recreation" and "tourism".*

Keywords: *recreational tourism, socio-economic resources, tourism opportunities, landscape, cultural heritage.*

INTRODUCTION

Tourism entered the world economy in the 21st century as a socio-economic field with a great positive impact. According to the information of the World Tourism Organization, 10% of the production and service turnover in the world is accounted for by tourism. The development of international tourism in the next 20 years is notable for the strong export of goods and services in the world market. That is, the export of tourist services has increased by 8% and makes up 30-35% of the global trade of general services. It is noted that the steady growth of the tourist flow will increase by 3-5% every year. In this regard, in Uzbekistan, the necessary organizational and legal mechanisms for the development of the sector were created during the years of independence, and the government adopted relevant regulatory documents. Work in this direction continues today.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

According to the information of the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC), the tourism industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan is included in the list of ten rapidly developing countries. In the period of determining the future, the trend of providing tourist services to foreign citizens in the Republic of Uzbekistan is increasing. In the future, this situation will ensure the development of the tourist business in the inbound and outbound tourism market of Uzbekistan, not only the tourism industry, but also a number of other sectors of the national economy related to tourism. The largest segment of international tourism is recreational travel, which accounts for 60% of global international tourism.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Recreational tourism includes rest, treatment and other purposes. This concept covers all types of recreation (restoration) rest in tourism, including sanatorium-resort treatment. By the end of the 20th century, the concept of "recreation" acquired new areas. Tourists themselves, especially those who travel regularly and frequently, seek more adventures in their vacations, try to get maximum pleasure and diversify their free time with active activities.

Landscape therapy, which is widely used in recreational tourism, is a spa treatment method that has a beneficial effect on the human body in an area with a beautiful landscape. It helps to normalize the functions of the nervous system, cheerful mood, sleep and appetite. Natural and climatic resources are actively used in recreational tourism. As a result of the

process of direct contact with natural natural gifts under the favorable influence of the surrounding nature, healing occurs in the human body itself, and its emotional and mental state improves. Viewing the monuments of human culture enriches human thinking, getting to know the customs and traditions of other peoples serves the interpenetration of cultures and the development of mutual solidarity between peoples.

The assessment of the recreational potential of the area is based on a consistent analysis of the characteristics of all its elements. These features are grouped into three main blocks:

- biomedicine;
- psycho-aesthetic;
- functional and economical.

For many countries of the world, this type of tourism is the most common and popular. Recreational resources are necessary for the development of this type of tourism. Recreational resources are the most important part of the natural potential of the region. Moreover, their role in the formation and development of modern tourism in the region is constantly increasing, especially from an ecological and geographical point of view. Components of recreation resources are evaluated according to: terrain, water bodies, soil, vegetation, bioclimate, hydro-mineral, unique natural healing resources, historical and cultural potential. The level of use of natural components or entire geosystems, natural resources may be different depending on the specialization of the regional economy. Among the natural tourist resources, the main place is occupied by recreation resources, which serve as a basis for recreation and treatment of the country's residents and foreign tourists. Natural objects in smaller areas are called "nature monuments".

Natural monuments are unique, remarkable objects created by animate and inanimate nature: caves, waterfalls, amazingly shaped rocks, gorges, geysers, springs, amazing landforms, geological openings, huge old trees, historical monuments, etc.

Natural monuments are ecologically, scientifically, culturally, aesthetically and historically unique, irreplaceable, valuable, nationally, regionally and locally important natural and anthropogenic objects of various origins. They differ in origin, content, purpose and importance. Depending on their general characteristics, natural monuments are divided into geological-geomorphological, botanical, paleontological, astronomical and landscape monuments.

Geological-geomorphological monuments include exposed rock layers, caves, karst landforms, extinguished volcanic craters, geysers, remarkable coasts, sheep's foreheads, unique landforms, rocks, and others. For example, objects such as Karaqizsoy in the Ugom mountain range, Teshik-tash Aksokota 5 km above the confluence of Aksokota in the Aksokota valley, karst processes on Alizar mountain, Obi-Rahmat, Shildiroq, Gormozor caves are a clear example.

Examples of paleontological monuments are places where fossilized remains of plants and traces of them have been found, as well as places where the remains and traces of extinct animals are found. For example, Khojakent petroglyphs in the Alizar Mountains are included.

Landscape monuments include magnificent rocks, waterfalls, gorges, wonderful springs, picturesque places. This includes Nanay waterfall, Aroshon spring, Shirinbulok, Katta and Kichik Chimyon brooks, Aktash brook in Aksarsoy creek.

Monuments of astronomical nature include places where large meteorites have fallen. One such place is the Observatory, which occupies an area of 1 hectare on Bogizilal Street in Burchmulla.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be noted that in order to develop tourism, scientific study of its natural geography will be of great importance in the future. For this, it is necessary to pay attention to their ecological characteristics in tourist use.

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